

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IS THE BASIS OF THE TEACHER'S ACTIVITY

Turmanov Kuatbay Amanbaevich

Pedagogical skill center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan,
Associate Professor.
Uzbekistan, Nukus.

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Abstract: This article talks about professional development of teachers in the process of professional development, professional development of teachers in the continuous professional development system.

Key words: Education system, process of continuous professional development, professional competence, professional development system, teacher's professional competence.

The strategic direction of the development of the education system in society is the intellectual and moral development of a person based on his purposeful independent activity in various fields. In the developed countries of the world, in the process of educational reforms, the promotion of independent education is considered as an important direction. The research of the phenomenon of education of the teacher's professional competence is expressed in the works of a number of scientists. These authors put forward the idea that together with the qualities of professional competence and reliability, the teacher's pedagogical culture is characterized as a professional and individual phenomenon.

In turn, the concept of professional competence, as stated by V.A. Slatsenin, represents the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the pedagogue to carry out pedagogical activities and describes his professional formation [1].

Formation of teacher's professional competence occupies a special place among the main problems of continuous professional development of pedagogues. Especially at the current stage of reforms related to the modernization of education, the problem of adaptation to professional pedagogical activity is becoming more evident. It enriches teachers with practical, psychological, methodical, research types, as well as with the formation of professional competence of the teacher.

Diagnostic, communicative, management and projective training groups should be included in the essential characteristics of professional training. The pedagogue's cognitive activity is largely determined by the complexity,

dynamics, non-standardity of the things being studied, the influence of the boundaries that separate social phenomena, their search, uncertainty, which implies observation, the ability to model the interlocutor's inner world[2].

In this case, the characteristics of self-regulation are characterized by the need to constantly improve one's knowledge and skills, and the ability to strictly coordinate one's behavior towards other people. In the works dedicated to the research of the professional training ability of the teacher, it is distinguished by the following types:

- special educational qualification;
- having a sufficiently high level of professional activity;
- the ability to plan one's future professional development;
- ability of social upbringing;
- mastering joint professional activity, cooperation, as well as professional communication methods adopted in this book, social responsibility for the results of one's profession.

The teacher's professional competence is formed on the basis of voluntary qualities, intellectual potential, emotional qualities, practical skills, interdependence of self-management abilities and individual qualities reflecting the level of socio-cultural activity of a person.

According to the tradition formed in European countries, professional qualification is measured by the competence of a specialist, and the educational system aimed at its formation is measured by the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

The following can be recognized as important pedagogical conditions in the professional development of teachers:

- normative and educational-methodical documents that can meet modern requirements (state educational standards, model curricula, working curricula, model training programs, working programs, textbooks, training programs availability of manuals, methodological recommendations, additional special literature, instructional tools, lesson plans, projects, etc.);

- high level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of scientific pedagogical staff (professors, associate professors, teachers, qualified tutors, technicians), sufficiently developed level of professional competence and having scientific potential;

- material and technical equipment of the educational process (educational buildings, educational auditoriums, educational workshops, practical-laboratory equipment), information technologies (radio, television, computer,

photocopiers, laboratory equipment, audio, video, multimedia, simulators, film projectors, slide projectors, video projectors, availability of a set of technical tools, etc.) is sufficiently provided;

- the creation of a socially and educationally technologically favorable environment (teachers, students, leaders and students, as well as the content, direction, unity of goals, etc. of mutual relations of students);

- consistent, continuous and systematic implementation of organizational and educational-practical activities.

Summarizing the definitions and descriptions given to the concept of "professional competence of a teacher", it can be interpreted as follows: Professional competence of a teacher is one of the important aspects of professional competence in the activity of a pedagogue. It represents all needs, abilities, skills, knowledge and interests.

For this he:

- tend to manage the process of creative research;

- it should be remembered that the effectiveness of creative research depends on the pedagogical, psychological and theoretical preparation of the teacher.

In the formation of professional competence, a desire for full professional formation, perception of pedagogical-technological situations, including the ability to expand the scope of professional interests, is a demand for self-improvement.

References:

1. V.A.Slatsenin. Pedagogy / V.A.Slatsenin. -M.: Shkola-Press, 2000.

2. Turgunov S.T., and others, "Development of professional skills and competence of teachers" - T.: "Sano-Standart", 2012.

